

Optimization of the synthesis and characterizations of chemical bath deposited Cu Doped ZnS thin films

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Abstract

A cost effective chemical route is used to synthesize ZnS: Cu nanocomposites. Zinc Sulphide is an important II-VI group semiconductor material possessing superior physico-chemical and optoelectronic characteristics like wide band gap, high chemical stability, large electrochemical coupling coefficient and good photochemical capacity. Further, transparent and conducting ZnS films have found various applications in optoelectronic technology due to its suitable optical, electrical and structural properties. Band gaps were determined using optical absorption measurements and carrier transport properties using conductivity measurements. The thickness of these films was controlled by changing the dipping times and the concentrations of the reaction solution. Experiments showed that the growth parameters and thermal treatment influenced the structure, the morphology and the optical properties of ZnS: Cu films. Structure properties of the films were measured using X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy in the as-deposited and annealed state. The result shows that thermal annealing promotes the growth of grains, decreases band gap, and enhances electrical conductivity

Keywords: Thin films; chemical bath deposition; Structure; Optical properties

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